

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B299
Date: 24 June 2007
Take Off: 09:36:22
Landing: 14:38:46
Flight Time: 5h 02m 24s

Campaign: GERBIL

Operating Area: Niamey -> Nouakchott

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM1	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
4	Core Chem.	Kate Turnbull	FAAM
5	Flight Manager	Jim Crawford	FAAM
6	Mission Scientist 1	Jim Haywood	Met Office
7	Mission Scientist 2	Ben Johnson	Met Office
8	AVAPS	Doug Anderson	FAAM
9	Filters	Paula Formenti	University of Paris 12 (LISA)
10	ARIES	Stuart Rogers	Met Office
11	CCM2	Jackie Mulholland	Directflight
12	Neph / PSAP / SWS	Andy Wilson	Met Office
13	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
14	Mission Scientist 3	Christian Gram	Leeds University
15	DFL Ops	Keith Drummond	Directflight

Flight Track:

B299 Track 24-JUN-07

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B299
 Date: 24 June 2007
 Project: GERBIL
 Location: Niamey -> Nouakchott

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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091718		inu	0.74 kft	102	to nav
091734		cgps	0.74 kft	102	B299cgps.log
092821		ASP	0.74 kft	086	open
093130		video	0.71 kft	098	#1 ffc , #2 ufc
093152		pirouette	0.71 kft	129	130M
093440		pirouette	0.71 kft	130	stop
093622		t/o	0.72 kft	266	niamey
093650	095846	Profile 1	1.1 - 22.0 kft	266	start at t/o
093715		Video	1.4 kft	269	#2 change to dfc
093732		psap	1.6 kft	270	flow on at t/o
093754		heimann	2.0 kft	269	open at 1000ft
095518		psap	18.2 kft	335	flow off 09:50, on 09:55
095554		P1	18.9 kft	335	roc increase, above dust
095804		psap	21.4 kft	324	flow off
095846	102332	Run 1.1	22.0 kft	323	
095950		psap	22.0 kft	324	flow on
100743		bbr	22.0 kft	325	retract
101314		JW	22.0 kft	325	zero
101347		Sonde 1	22.0 kft	325	
102332	104259	Profile 2	22.0 - 3.1 kft	335	
102412		heimann	21.3 kft	336	cal 12
102423		bbr	21.2 kft	335	extend
104300	105801	Run 2.1	3.1 kft	330	
104532		!	3.1 kft	291	turn onto track
104547		bbr	3.1 kft	268	retract
105138		bbr	3.1 kft	269	rawdata check
105205		JW	3.1 kft	270	check
105229		Heimann	3.1 kft	271	check
105250		heimann	3.1 kft	271	cal 14
105801	105920	Profile 3	3.1 - 2.1 kft	269	
105921	111309	Run 3.1	2.1 kft	269	
110142		Video	2.1 kft	270	#1 & #2 end
111228		psap	2.1 kft	268	filter change 11:10:00 (F1 ->F2)
111450	112814	Profile 4	2.2 - 15.0 kft	096	
111501		bbr extend	2.4 kft	097	
112844		bbr	15.0 kft	050	retract
113025	115131	Run 4.1	15.0 - 15.1 kft	261	
113825		Sonde 2	15.0 kft	272	
114529		sonde 2	15.0 kft	271	launch detect failure
115131	120152	Profile 5	15.1 - 24.0 kft	274	
115204		bbr	15.6 kft	273	extend
115311		heimann	16.5 kft	273	cal 14
120152	130059	Run 5.1	24.0 kft	271	
121250		Sonde 3	24.0 kft	270	
123441		video	24.0 kft	269	#3 & #4; end
123539		Video	24.0 kft	269	#5 ffc, #6 dfc; started
123911		Sonde 4	24.0 kft	270	
124325		Sonde 5	24.0 kft	270	
125811		Sonde 5	24.0 kft	271	
130100	132113	Profile 6	24.0 - 5.0 kft	270	
130312		bbr	21.8 kft	268	extend
132114	133935	Run 6.1	5.0 kft	269	
132134		bbr	5.0 kft	272	retract
132148		heimann	5.0 kft	271	cal 14
133936	134834	Profile 7	5.0 - 13.0 kft	269	
134834	140309	Run 7.1	13.0 kft	279	
135052		bbr	13.0 kft	278	retract
140310	140741	Profile 8	13.0 - 17.0 kft	276	
140741	142644	Profile 9	17.0 - 1.0 kft	276	

142003	P9	5.0 kft	290 interrupt
142154	resume	5.0 kft	105
143846	Land	0.00 kft	222 Nouakchott
143919	psap	0.01 kft	218 flow off

B299 Track 24-JUN-07

FAAM sortie brief

GERBILS

Flight No: B299

24th June 2007

Objectives

1. Measure the radiative effect of Saharan dust over the desert.
2. Insitu sampling of Saharan dust.

Location

From Niamey to Nouakchott over desert areas.

Desired weather

High dust loadings. Clear skies.

Special requirements

Dropsondes.

Instruments of importance

Nephelometers (wet and dry)

PCASP

PSAP

BBRs

SWS

ARIES

Flight pattern

1. Take off from Niamey at 10Z (11L).
2. Profile climb to above dust layer at 1000ft/min, then accelerate climb to FL220 once above dust [20mins].
3. SLR at FL220 altitude towards 18N 1W [30mins, T=50mins].
4. Drop a sonde 12mins after start of high-level SLR.
5. At 18N 1W profile down to MPA at max descent rate above dust, then 1000ft/min in dust layer [20mins, T=70mins].
6.
 - a. If cloud free perform SLR at MPA for 15mins. SWS to increment through a range of angles "scanning run", ARIES to point up.
 - b. If low-level clouds are found perform profile ascent to a level above low cloud and perform item 6a at that altitude [15mins, T=85mins].
7. Perform a series of SLRs within the dust layer (heights to be determined by mission scientist, suggest. FL075 and FL150). Profiles inbetween at 1000ft/min [50mins, T=135mins].
8. Profile ascent to a level above dust at 1000ft/min then accelerate climb to range altitude. One of these runs on reciprocal heading [10mins, T=145mins].
9. SLR at high-level towards Nouakchott. Drop one sonde on reaching top of profile then every 30mins whilst at high level [125mins, 260mins].
10. Profile descent into Nouakchott [25mins, T=285mins].
11. Land Nouakchot.

Mission scientist debrief

B299 – GERBILS flight Niamey to Nouakchott

Location

Along 18N from 1W to 16W.

Mission aims

Radiative effect of Saharan dust over North Africa. Insitu sampling of Saharan dust aerosol.

Weather

Mostly clear skies. Some mid and high level cloud around north-west of Niger and passing corner of Burkina Faso. Some cirrus also 12-15W.

Flight plans

Pirouette done. No cloud observed at Niamey although a bit hazy to so not easy to judge absolutely. Take off at 09:36Z followed by a profile climb to FL220 heading towards 18N 1W. A 25min high level run with 1 sonde dropped mid-way along run. Profile descent to MPA (3000ft) at just before reaching 18N 1W followed by a 15min run with SWS scanning through a range of angles. Dust aerosol top was around FL170. Aerosol concentration not particularly high in most of profile (50-100) but then rose to several hundred $\times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$ in a slightly cooler shallow layer below 4000ft. Ground surface was 800ft altitude. Dropped down (in profile) to 2000ft due to increasing visibility and 15min run at 2000ft with 2mins of SWS nadir viewing and 13min of zenith viewing. Reciprocal turn and profile ascent to FL150 followed by reciprocal turn and run for 20mins at FL150. Neph was only 30 on the FL150 run. Climb up to FL240 and a run for about an hour. Mostly cloud free along this run. Three sondes dropped along this run. At 10.5W a descent was made to 5000ft followed by a 18min run at that level. A climb to FL130 and a 15min run at that level. Then a quick climb to FL170 and a drop back down to 1000ft finishing over the ocean NW of Noakchott. Recovery to 2000ft and land at Nouakchott at 14:38Z.

Summary

Excellent, cloud-free, radiation work over a 50mile path of a shallow dust storm over Mail. High and low-level runs over the same path plus a profile through the atmospheric column and a dropsonde through the centre. Good radiation work during high-level run along 18N with reasonably high dust optical depths (0.3-0.5) and very little cloud influence (tiny bit of cirrus). Good insitu sampling of high concentrations of dust on 3 runs. 3 deep profiles.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.299** Date **24/6/07** Name **Ben Johnson** Page **1** of **4**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
0933	Pirouette		130°		Slightly hazy, looks like cloud free
-0936					visibility quite high at low-level (30 30 km?)
093622	T10				
093622	P1	Sfc -FL220	270	NIAMEY	Turning to NW heading towards 18N 7W
095000					some mid-high cloud around in NW Niger as predicted by Christian's model
095100		FL140	335	14.1N 1.5E	Cloud penetration Taurasal ~ 0.35 Dust
095956	End	FL220	325	14.7N 1.2E	cirrus above, no cloud observed below
095956	P1.1	FL220	325	"	
101347	End	"	"	15.8N	
102332	End	"	"	0.4E	
102332	P2	PL220	335	16.5N 0.2W	Little bits of thin cirrus above but becoming less as we progress northwest.
1030	"	FL160	"		Dust top at FL160
1035					ozone decline from 85 85 to 45 ppbv.
1037		FL080			can't see surface yet see it by FL060

Ben Johnson

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GMT	Run/Prof	Alt	Hdg	GPS
104300	End P2			
104300	R 2.1	3,000	330	
105831	End R2.1 P3	3000 -2000ft		
105921	R3.1	2000ft		
111309	End R3.1 Reciprocal turn	2000ft		
111450	P4	15,000ft		

co working again from 1020 onwards

Ground 2,200 Ft below us but we are at MPA

Highly concentrated aerosol in shallow BL below 4000ft

Neph ~~at~~ 300-1000x10⁶ m⁻¹

Ground only just visible from window and downward camera.

1,100ft above terrain

SWS scanning run on R3.1 nadir & zenith on R3.1.

[Handwritten scribbles and signatures]

Mission Scientist's Log

41
15 mins
1.5

Flight No **B.299** Date **24/6/07** Name **Ben Johnson** Page **3** of **4**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11 2814	End P4	FL150	90	18N 2.5-15W	FL150
11 3025	R41	FL150	270	18N 16W	Rim just near top of dust layer with neph $\sim 30 \times 10^{-6} m^{-1}$ and above
11 3825	Drop Sndle 2	FL150	270		track where low-level work was completed.
11 5131	End R4.1	FL150			
11 5131	PS	FL150			no cirrus or other clouds observed
12 0152	End B	FL240			
12 0152	RS1	FL240	270	18N 14.5W	Surface albedo higher
12 1215	Sndle 3	"	"	18N 5.7W	From 2W-4W; from lower BRs and SWS.
12 3000	Sndle 4	"			little bit of cirrus at 12:13
12 3911	Sndle 4	"			Sndle 4 failed but regained signal below FL100
12 4325	Sndle 5	"			
12 5811	Sndle 6	"			
13 0100	P6	FL240		KONAD 18N 10.3W	Dust layer top at FL 150 ¹⁶⁵ corresponds to little inversion
13 2114	R6.1	FL050	270	18N 12W	Quite nice thick dust down here neph $\sim 200 \times 10^{-6} m^{-1}$
					SWS switch to nadir due to cloud above.
					AIRRES temporary loss of data
13 3946	End R6.1	"	"		

Mission Scientist's Log

11/30

Flight No **B.299** Date **26/6/07** Name **Ben Johnson** Page **4** of **4**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
133916	P7	FL050	133W 18N	270	
134834	R7.1	FL130	18N 14W	28S	Neph dropped down to 30-40 not so good
140310	PK	FL130 -FL170			# Dust top just above
140741	pg	FL170			reached at FL170
1426		-sfc			Bottom of profile over Ocean NW of Nauyaschott
1438	LAND				
	<u>Debrief</u>				Total time = 4:00 5:00
	PCASP1 working				
	ARIES				
	SWS				
	Chemistry ✓ sorted				
	Filters ✓				
	Good insitu sampling 5 runs 3 of which had high dust concentrations				
Good	Radiation work at low-level plus vertical profile through and high-level run above. Same place.				

Good long high-level run with minimal cloud interference and significant dust below all the way. 3 deep profiles

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG FOR FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight Number : B299

Date : 24/06/07

Operator and contact info : Kate Turnbull katet@faam.ac.uk

Problems with Instruments

CO	Leak to cabin air isolated during initial profile. Data believed correct from 1020Z.
O₃	None
NO_x	None
TDLAS	None

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 299

Date: 24/06/07	Operator: 08:30:00	DRS Time: +0	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
																Start P1 from Takeoff	
09:39:15	375	0.08	1	1	1											FL030	
09:40:27	330	0.08		20	2											FL040	
09:41:27	260	0.09		15	2											FL050	
09:42:21	180	0.10	2	30	3											FL060	
09:43:18	150	0.11		50	2											FL070	
09:44:21	150	0.11		40	3											FL080	
09:45:31	160	0.11		60	8											FL090	
09:46:37	100	0.11		50	2											FL100	
09:47:44	110	0.11	3	30	3											FL110	
09:48:47	100	0.11		30	3											FL120	
09:49:54	100	0.11	4	40	6											FL130	
09:50:52	85	0.14		50	3											FL140	
09:52:05	60	0.12	20	1000	500											FL150	
09:53:12	10	0.09	37	5	100											FL160	
09:54:17	10	0.09		3	Noise											FL170	
09:55:14	2	0.11		3												FL180	
09:56:02	3	0.10		2	10											FL190	
09:57:00	1	0.06		1	10											FL200	
09:57:50	1	0.06		10	2	2	800								8	FL210	
09:58:46	180	0.15	38	90	10											End of P1 & Start Run 1 @ FL220	
10:00:00	5	0.08	39	2													
10:05:00	5	0.08															
10:10:00	3	0.06		1													
10:15:00	3	0.07		1													
10:20:00	2	0.07		1	1												
10:23:33																End of Run 1.1 & Start P2 from FL220	
10:24:32	5	0.06		1												FL210	
10:25:40	2	0.07														FL200	
10:26:38	5	0.07														FL190	
10:27:34	3	0.07		1												FL180	
10:28:43	5	0.08		1	4											FL170	
10:29:50	10	0.09		3	8											FL160	
10:30:55	40	0.11		10	5											FL150	
10:31:49	60	0.10		10	3											FL140	
10:32:46	70	0.10		20	3											FL130	
10:33:38	100	0.10	40	30	10											FL120	
10:34:43	115	0.11		40	10											FL110	
10:35:44	125	0.11		50	10											FL100	
10:37:06	130	0.12	41	60	10											FL090 PCASP heater OFF	
10:38:52	150	0.12		80	10											FL080	
10:39:53	170	0.12	42	80	10											FL070	
10:40:55	190	0.12	43	90	10											FL060	
10:41:55	500	0.15	45	300	30											FL040	
10:43:00																End of P2 & Start Run 2.1 @ FL030	
10:45:00	400	0.15	71	200	20												

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 299

Date: 24/06/07	Operator: 08:30:00	DRS Time: +0	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 2 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
10:47:00	410	0.14	77	200	10	1	300										
10:49:00	300	0.14	82	100	10	1											
10:51:00	220	0.14	84	90	10												
10:53:00	280	0.15	85	100	10	1											
10:55:00	320	0.14	88	150	10	1	200										
10:57:00	270	0.15	89	100	10												
10:58:01																End of Run 1 & Start P3 from FL030	
10:59:23																End of P3 & Start Run 3.1	
11:00:00	500	0.16	91	300	20	3	300										
11:02:00	450	0.17	95	200	20	1	300										
11:04:00	400	0.15	99	200	10	3											
11:06:00	400	0.16	104	200	10	2	300										
11:08:00	340	0.16	108	150	10	1.5	50										
11:10:00	310	0.16	112	150	10	2	300										
11:12:00	280	0.15	115	100	10	2	100										
11:13:10																End of Run 3.1	
11:14:49	300	0.14	119	100	10	1	400									Start P4 from FL020	
11:15:44	240	0.14	120	100	10	1										FL030	
11:16:39	260	0.13	120	90	10											FL040	
11:17:46	210	0.12	121	80	6											FL050	
11:18:42	180	0.12	122	70	7											FL060	
11:19:47	180	0.12		80	6											FL070	
11:20:48	150	0.11	123	70	6											FL080	
11:21:49	150	0.12		60	5											FL090	
11:22:50	105	0.11		10	5											FL100	
11:23:56	90	0.12		20	2											FL110	
11:25:04	100	0.12		15	1											FL120 PCASP Heaters ON	
11:26:08	85	0.10		15	1											FL130	
11:27:13	60	0.11	124	10	1											FL140	
11:28:14	55	0.12		10	1											End of P4 @ FL150	
11:30:25																Start Run 4.1 @ FL150	
11:31:00	45	0.12		10	1												
11:33:00	55	0.10		10	1												
11:35:00	70	0.09		10	1												
11:37:00	70	0.11		10	1												
11:39:00	60	0.12		10	1												
11:41:00	70	0.11		10	1												
11:43:00	55	0.11	125	15	2												
11:45:00	60	0.12	126	15	1												
11:47:00	85	0.12		15	1												
11:49:00	80	0.10	127	15	1												
11:51:00	80	0.11	128	15	1												
11:51:20																End of Run 4.1 & Start P5 from FL150	
11:52:36	70	0.11		15	1											FL160	
11:53:44	70	0.10		20	1											FL170	
11:54:59	30	0.15	129	5	1											FL180	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 299

Date: 24/06/07	Operator: 08:30:00	DRS Time: +0	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 3 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
11:56:03	3	0.09	129	2	1											FL190	
11:57:26	1	0.09		2	1											FL200	
11:58:22	2	0.09		1	1											FL210	
11:59:33	2	0.09		1	1											FL220	
12:00:33	2	0.07		1	2											FL230	
12:01:52																End of P5 & Start Run 5.1 @ FL240	
12:05:00	1	0.07		1	5												
12:10:00	3	0.07		1	Noise												
12:15:00	2	0.09		1	Noise												
12:20:00				1													
12:25:00	1	0.04		1	1												
12:30:00	1	0.03		1	1												
12:35:00	1	0.06	130	1	1												
12:40:00	2	0.04		1	1												
12:45:00	1	0.04		1	1												
12:50:00	2	0.06		1	1												
12:55:00	1	0.04		1	1												
13:00:00	1	0.04		1	1												
13:00:53																End of Run 5.1 & Start P6 from FL240	
13:02:00	3	0.07		1												FL230	
13:02:54	2	0.06		1	1											FL220	
13:03:54	1	0.07		1	1											FL210	
13:05:03	4	0.11		1	1											FL200	
13:06:10	4	0.14		2	1											FL190	
13:07:25	8	0.15		5	1											FL180	
13:08:33	10	0.13		5	1											FL170	
13:09:35	50	0.17	131	20	5											FL160	
13:10:49	50	0.15		30	2											FL150	
13:11:51	80	0.14		50	4											FL140	
13:12:49	95	0.13	132	50	4											FL130	
13:13:53	100	0.12		40	4											FL120	
13:14:51	100	0.12	133	50	5											FL110	
13:15:50	75	0.13	134	40	10											FL100	
13:17:03	120	0.13		50	8											FL090 PCASP heater OFF	
13:18:03	165	0.12	136	80	8											FL080	
13:19:03	200	0.12	143	90	10											FL070	
13:20:16	260	0.13	150	90	20											FL060	
13:21:14																End of P6 & Start Run 6.1 @ FL050	
13:22:00	270	0.15	151	150	20												
13:24:00	280	0.14	153	120	20												
13:26:00	220	0.12	154	90	10												
13:28:00	210	0.11	155	80	10												
13:30:00	220	0.11	156	80	10												
13:32:00	220	0.11	157	70	10												
13:34:00	225	0.11	158	70	10												
13:36:00	230	0.10	159	70	8												

Filter Sampling Log

Flight No:

B299

Date:

24 JUN 2007

Operator:

Type of filters mounted in	Top inlet	47 mm Nuclepore (0.4 µm pore size)	Bottom inlet	47 mm Nuclepore (0.4 µm pore size)
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Run No	Disk #1 TOP	Disk #2 MIDDLE	Disk #3 BOTTOM	Inlet Top/ Bottom	Time On	Time Off	Flight Run	Accum Vol [l]	Comments
Filters run1	260-07	----	----	Bottom	10:43:00	11:13:09	R2.1/R3.1	1119	R2.1 3000 feet, sigma_scatt ~600 Mm-1, sigma_scatt ~180 Mm-1 @12h52
Filters run1	259-07	----	----	Top	10:43:00	11:13:09	R2.1/R3.1	1554	
Filters run 2	262-07	----	----	Bottom	11:32:00	11:51:31		217	FL150 top of aerosols layer, sigma_scatt ~30 Mm-1, 18.1N 9W
Filters run 2	263-07	----	----	Top	11:32:00	11:51:31		512	
Filters run 3_a	264-07	----	----	Bottom	13:21:14	13:39:35	R6.1	567	R6.1 FL050, sigma_scatt ~230 Mm-1, sigma_scatt ~120 Mm-1 @13h27, sigma_scatt ~95 Mm-1 @13h33,
Filters run 3_a	271-07	----	----	Top	13:21:14	13:39:35	R6.1	863	
Filters run 3_b	264-07	----	----	Bottom	13:48:34	14:03:00	R7.1	212	R6.1 FL050, sigma_scatt ~230 Mm-1, sigma_scatt ~120 Mm-1 @13h27, sigma_scatt ~95 Mm-1 @13h33,
Filters run 3_b	271-07	----	----	Top	13:48:34	14:03:00	R7.1	450	
Filters run 4	272-07	----	----	Bottom	----	----	----	----	BLANK
Filters run 4	265-07	----	----	Top	----	----	----	----	BLANK

B299_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog.txt

```

08:38:24.71 --- - - - -
08:38:24.71 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
08:38:24.71 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
                                tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
08:38:24.71 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B299
08:38:24.71 --- - - - -
08:38:42.78 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
08:38:44.92 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
08:38:45.88 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
08:38:50.65 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
08:38:54.36 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
08:38:57.97 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:38:57.97 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:38:57.98 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:39:04.04 SWS - - 350 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 350ms.
08:39:07.45 SWS - - 500 - VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 500ms.
08:39:09.90 SWS - - - 500 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 500ms.
08:39:13.39 USH - - 500 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 500ms.
08:39:16.12 USH - - - 400 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 400ms.
08:39:18.85 LSH - - 400 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 400ms.
08:39:21.75 LSH - - - 750 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 750ms.
08:39:24.65 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:39:24.69 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:39:25.11 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:39:30.14 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:39:30.28 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:39:32.43 SWS - - - - Idling
08:39:33.07 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:39:33.68 USH - - - - Idling
08:39:35.58 LSH - - - - Idling
09:25:30.68 --- - - - - *** preflight ok
09:26:04.67 --- - - - - *** B299 Gerbils flight Niamey to Nouakchott
09:26:12.91 --- - - - - *** taxiing
09:26:25.11 --- - - - - *** sws to 90Aft for take off
09:26:30.51 --- - - - - *** data start
09:26:40.74 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:26:40.75 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:26:40.75 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:26:47.45 USH - - 250 - VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 250ms.
09:26:51.48 USH - - 75 - VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 75ms.
09:26:57.57 SWS - - 200 - VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 200ms.
09:27:02.49 SWS - - - 350 NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 350ms.
09:27:07.81 SWS - - 150 - VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 150ms.
09:27:11.55 LSH - - 750 - VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 750ms.
09:27:19.43 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:27:19.45 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:27:19.51 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:27:23.38 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:27:24.07 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:27:27.77 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:27:38.25 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:27:42.18 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:27:43.63 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:27:47.29 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:27:48.07 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:27:55.23 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:27:58.16 --- - - - - *** shutters inop resetting
09:28:02.89 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
09:28:07.31 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
09:28:14.81 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:28:18.17 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:28:18.76 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:28:22.57 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:28:22.60 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:28:30.51 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:28:35.70 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:28:36.05 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.

```

09:28:36.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:28:39.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:28:40.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:28:44.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:28:52.08	---	-	-	-	-	*** shutters ok
09:37:08.22	---	-	-	-	-	*** take off 20 second ago
09:38:13.40	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
09:38:25.94	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws to 9F for climb out
09:40:09.46	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 100ms.
09:40:11.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:40:15.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:50:26.93	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud above
09:51:00.95	---	-	-	-	-	*** passing throughd
09:55:57.98	---	-	-	-	-	*** at FL180 and between cloud layers
09:58:59.91	---	-	-	-	-	*** r1.1end profile and start
09:59:25.35	---	-	-	-	-	*** end profile and start R1.1
09:59:42.14	---	-	-	-	-	*** at FL22
09:59:48.96	---	-	-	-	-	*** FL20
09:59:55.52	---	-	-	-	-	*** FL220
10:00:09.88	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
10:00:17.27	SWS	-	-	-	250	NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 250ms.
10:00:21.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:00:22.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:00:22.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:00:25.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:00:26.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:00:29.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:08:48.69	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 400ms.
10:08:53.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:09:00.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:09:46.84	---	-	-	-	-	*** clear from cloud above now
10:19:55.82	---	-	-	-	-	*** occasional thin Ci above
10:20:04.55	USH	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 50ms.
10:20:08.25	USH	-	-	-	350	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 350ms.
10:20:12.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:20:12.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:20:12.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:20:14.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:20:16.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:20:20.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:24:37.12	---	-	-	-	-	*** good dust layer below
10:28:51.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:28:51.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:28:51.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:28:54.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:28:55.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:28:59.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:29:14.35	---	-	-	-	-	*** at FL165 descending
10:29:21.15	---	-	-	-	-	*** still above dust
10:30:58.54	---	-	-	-	-	*** in dust
10:31:26.44	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
10:31:32.34	SWS	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 250ms to 400ms.
10:31:36.20	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 750ms.
10:31:39.66	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
10:31:42.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:31:50.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:34:02.10	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 150ms.
10:34:06.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:34:14.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:36:11.89	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 100ms.
10:36:14.42	SWS	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
10:36:16.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:36:22.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:39:30.30	SWS	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 400ms.
10:39:34.16	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 75ms.
10:39:36.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:39:40.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:39:41.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:39:45.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

10:39:55.73	---	-	-	-	*** at FL060 in dust
10:41:13.15	SWS	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 300ms.
10:41:15.72	SWS	-	-	50	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 50ms.
10:41:17.53	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:41:20.96	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:42:17.61	SWS	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
10:42:24.13	SWS	-	-	25	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 25ms.
10:42:27.81	SWS	-	-	150	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 150ms.
10:42:30.92	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:42:32.85	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:43:02.75	---	-	-	-	*** SWS to beginscanning run
10:43:13.22	---	-	-	-	*** end P2 start R2.1
10:43:42.27	---	-	-	-	*** SWS to 50 AFT
10:43:57.73	SWS	-	-	75	VIS int.time changed from 25ms to 75ms.
10:44:01.28	SWS	-	-	250	NIR int.time changed from 150ms to 250ms.
10:44:04.64	SWS	-	-	350	NIR int.time changed from 250ms to 350ms.
10:44:08.98	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:44:12.92	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:44:40.23	---	-	-	-	*** SWS to 50 Forward
10:45:51.50	---	-	-	-	*** SWS to 40Aft
10:46:37.65	---	-	-	-	*** change of heading from 330 to 270degrees
10:46:46.63	SWS	-	-	50	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 50ms.
10:46:52.73	SWS	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 200ms.
10:46:54.73	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:46:57.16	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:47:04.98	---	-	-	-	*** sws to 40 fore
10:48:21.92	---	-	-	-	*** swsto 30AFT
10:48:33.68	SWS	-	-	10	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 10ms.
10:48:37.60	SWS	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
10:48:39.33	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:48:40.76	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:49:51.16	---	-	-	-	*** SWS to 30 FORE
10:50:00.07	SWS	-	-	75	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 75ms.
10:50:03.72	SWS	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 300ms.
10:50:05.67	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:50:09.12	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:50:31.16	LSH	-	-	250	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 250ms.
10:50:34.24	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:50:42.17	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:51:01.91	---	-	-	-	*** sws to 20 AFT
10:51:20.25	SWS	-	-	10	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 10ms.
10:51:22.73	SWS	-	-	150	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 150ms.
10:51:25.76	SWS	-	-	75	NIR int.time changed from 150ms to 75ms.
10:51:28.61	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:51:29.80	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:52:29.31	---	-	-	-	*** sws to 20 FORE
10:52:42.63	SWS	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 75ms to 300ms.
10:52:47.02	SWS	-	-	150	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 150ms.
10:52:51.20	SWS	-	-	75	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 75ms.
10:52:53.89	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:52:57.32	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:53:58.09	---	-	-	-	*** SWS to 10 AFT
10:54:08.28	SWS	-	-	25	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 25ms.
10:54:10.92	SWS	-	-	75	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 75ms.
10:54:13.08	SWS	-	-	10	VIS int.time changed from 25ms to 10ms.
10:54:15.56	SWS	-	-	25	NIR int.time changed from 75ms to 25ms.
10:54:18.02	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:54:18.71	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:55:18.10	---	-	-	-	*** SWS to 10 FORE
10:55:26.22	SWS	-	-	150	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 150ms.
10:55:31.09	SWS	-	-	50	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 50ms.
10:55:36.82	SWS	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 25ms to 100ms.
10:55:41.74	SWS	-	-	150	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 150ms.
10:55:45.14	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:55:47.09	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:56:50.12	---	-	-	-	*** SWS to 0 deg zenith
10:57:00.05	SWS	-	-	25	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 25ms.
10:57:02.78	SWS	-	-	75	NIR int.time changed from 150ms to 75ms.
10:57:18.61	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

10:57:19.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:58:27.80	---	-	-	-	-	*** end scanning start Profile descent
10:59:36.81	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
10:59:45.76	---	-	-	-	-	*** 2
11:00:04.60	---	-	-	-	-	*** 2 mins nadir vier
11:00:08.19	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 25ms to 75ms.
11:00:10.65	SWS	-	-	-	150	NIR int.time changed from 75ms to 150ms.
11:00:14.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:00:16.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:01:55.74	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:02:00.21	SWS	-	-	25	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 25ms.
11:02:03.79	SWS	-	-	-	75	NIR int.time changed from 150ms to 75ms.
11:02:06.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:02:07.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:02:10.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:02:10.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:02:11.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:02:11.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:02:14.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:02:19.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:10:39.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:10:40.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:10:40.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:10:41.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:10:44.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:10:48.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:13:12.88	---	-	-	-	-	*** end run
11:15:04.16	---	-	-	-	-	*** start P4
11:18:22.70	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 75ms to 200ms.
11:18:27.29	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 25ms to 50ms.
11:18:31.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:18:34.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:18:36.97	LSH	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 350ms.
11:18:40.58	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 400ms.
11:18:45.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:18:53.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:21:37.15	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws to 8F during climp
11:21:51.06	SWS	-	-	25	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 25ms.
11:21:52.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:21:55.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:21:58.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:21:58.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:21:58.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:22:00.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:22:02.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:22:06.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:28:19.24	---	-	-	-	-	*** end p4
11:28:25.68	---	-	-	-	-	*** at FL150
11:29:12.31	---	-	-	-	-	*** turning to reciprocal heading of 270 degrees
11:30:12.04	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
11:30:25.89	---	-	-	-	-	*** for SLR at FL150
11:30:30.26	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 25ms to 75ms.
11:30:34.02	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 100ms.
11:30:40.51	LSH	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 300ms.
11:30:44.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:30:44.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:30:44.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:30:47.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:30:48.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:30:52.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:32:00.84	---	-	-	-	-	*** heading 254 deg
11:32:43.51	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws to 175 rear
11:32:58.19	---	-	-	-	-	*** ac pitch 4.7 deg
11:34:32.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** heading 270 degrees
11:50:16.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:50:17.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:50:17.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:50:19.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

11:50:20.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:50:25.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:52:11.94	---	-	-	-	-	*** end run start profile
11:54:56.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws to 172 AFT for climb
11:56:10.36	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 75ms.
11:56:13.74	USH	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 300ms.
11:56:17.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:56:18.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:56:18.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:56:20.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:56:21.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:56:26.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:02:08.31	---	-	-	-	-	*** end profile and start R5.1 at FL240
12:03:13.68	LSH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
12:03:16.33	LSH	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
12:03:18.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:03:23.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:05:09.61	---	-	-	-	-	*** increase in Lower shims due to lighter coloured desert below
12:05:51.95	---	-	-	-	-	*** lighter coloured desert below
12:10:47.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:10:47.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:10:48.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:10:50.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:10:51.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:10:53.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:28:10.03	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
12:38:18.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:38:19.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:38:19.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:38:21.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:38:22.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:38:24.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:01:07.44	---	-	-	-	-	*** end run start profile descent
13:09:08.53	---	-	-	-	-	*** SWS to 176 AFT during profile descent
13:09:31.60	LSH	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 350ms.
13:09:35.24	LSH	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
13:09:38.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:09:38.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:09:38.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:09:40.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:09:42.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:09:46.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:21:14.04	---	-	-	-	-	*** ed profile at 5000ft start run
13:21:25.98	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
13:21:30.04	SWS	-	-	25	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 25ms.
13:21:33.51	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 25ms to 10ms.
13:21:36.73	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 50ms.
13:21:42.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:21:42.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:21:42.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:21:43.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:21:45.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:21:50.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:23:23.54	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud above
13:24:10.57	---	-	-	-	-	***
13:24:10.67	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
13:24:18.11	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 75ms.
13:24:21.06	SWS	-	-	-	150	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 150ms.
13:24:28.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:24:30.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:29:07.38	USH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
13:29:11.88	USH	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 500ms.
13:29:17.93	SWS	-	-	-	250	NIR int.time changed from 150ms to 250ms.
13:29:20.65	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 100ms.
13:29:24.51	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 150ms.
13:29:32.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:29:32.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:29:32.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

13:29:35.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:29:38.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:29:40.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:32:47.13	USH	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
13:32:49.96	USH	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 300ms.
13:32:53.39	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 100ms.
13:32:56.96	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 250ms to 200ms.
13:32:58.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:32:58.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:32:59.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:33:01.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:33:02.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:33:07.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:38:46.53	---	-	-	-	-	*** SWS nadir view showing unusual vis returns
13:39:11.98	---	-	-	-	-	*** strong peak in the red band approx 700nm
13:39:45.00	---	-	-	-	-	*** end r6.1 start P7
13:40:10.95	---	-	-	-	-	*** still cloud above
13:48:17.28	---	-	-	-	-	*** end P7 start R7.1
13:49:31.38	---	-	-	-	-	*** scattered ac an ci clouds above
13:59:54.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:59:54.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:59:54.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:59:57.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:59:58.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:59:59.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:00:00.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:00:02.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:00:02.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:00:03.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:00:14.81	---	-	-	-	-	*** shutters inop resetting
14:00:17.06	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
14:00:21.63	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
14:00:27.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:00:28.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:00:29.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:00:31.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:00:32.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:00:39.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:03:58.42	---	-	-	-	-	*** end run
14:05:05.50	---	-	-	-	-	*** climbing to FL170
14:06:09.35	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 75ms.
14:06:14.68	LSH	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 300ms.
14:06:18.81	LSH	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
14:06:22.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:06:22.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:06:22.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:06:24.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:06:26.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:06:27.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:07:48.54	---	-	-	-	-	*** start P9 to 100ft over ocean
14:08:36.58	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud above so SWS kept in Nadir view
14:16:31.96	---	-	-	-	-	*** over oean at FL100
14:16:43.31	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 750ms.
14:16:48.11	LSH	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
14:16:52.14	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 200ms.
14:16:56.90	SWS	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 500ms.
14:17:00.90	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
14:17:05.94	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 300ms.
14:17:11.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:17:11.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:17:11.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:17:14.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:17:19.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:17:19.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:21:22.78	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
14:21:32.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:21:40.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:24:34.88	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
14:26:58.83	---	-	-	-	-	*** end P9 at 1000ft

14:27:24.37 --- - - - - *** recover to Nouakchott
14:28:23.96 --- - - - - *** overland on approach data stop

ARIES flight log

Flight: B299

page 1 of 3

Date: 24/Jan/2007

Operator(s): S. ROGERS

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: NIAMEY TO NOUAKCHOTT.

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shttr	HBB	CBB	Comments
08 43 36	on the pan	1x60	CH	C	71	41	Script 1
08 43 36	THW30ff						
09 53 48	FL220	1x60	CH	C	61	40	MBS=60? adjusting...
10 00 49	rev	"	CH	C	71	38	
10 02 18	FL220	480x1	N	C	71	42	Thick dust below
10 06 32		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
10 07 49		480x1	N	C	71	41	
10 11 53		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
10 13 09		480x1	N	C	71	41	
10 17 12		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
10 18 40		480x1	N	C	71	41	
10 22 42		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
	rev	480x1					
10 43 00	3000ft	1x60	CH	C	71	41	
10 44 30		360x1	Z	O	71	41	Opening shutter at first / turning
10 47 40		120x1	N	C	71	42	
10 48 47		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
10 50 08		360x1	Z	O	71	41	Aborted - used 360x60 by mistake
10 50 46		360x1	Z	O	70	41	
10 53 56		120x1	N	C	70	41	Surface visible.
10 55 00		1x60	CH	C	71	42	
10 56 34		120x1	Z	O	70	41	Shutter opening at start of view
10 58 09		1x60	CH	C	71	42	
10 59 25	1100ft	1x60	CH	C	71	42	
11 00 43		360x1	Z	O	71	41	
11 03 56		120x1	N	C	71	43	
11 05 02		1x60	CH	C	71	43	
11 06 20		360x1	Z	O	71	43	Shutter opening at start.
11 09 28		120x1	N	C	71	43	
11 16 32		1x60	CH	C	71	44	
	rev	1x60					
							CBS drifting upwards - turning off scanner to help it cool

ARIES flight log

Flight: B299

page 2 of 3

Date:

Operator(s):

Res:

Gain A: B:

Loc./Notes:

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
11 30 28	FL150	1x60	CH	C	71	41	
11 31 47	"	480x1	N	C	71	41	
11 35 47	"	1x60	CH	C	71	41	
11 37 17	"	360x1	N	C	71	41	
11 40 21	"	1x60	CH	C	71	42	
11 41 44		480x1	N	C	71	41	
11 45 44		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
11 47 06		480x1	N	C	71	41	
11 51 07		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
12 01 54	↑ FL240	1x60	CH	C	71	41	
12 03 11		480x1	N	C	71	41	
12 07 25		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
12 08 43		480x1	N	C	71	41	
12 12 46		1x60	CH	C	71	41	Oops - substantially by accident. (Hot view might be looking at 2!)
?		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
12 14 59		120x1	Z	O	70	41	
12 16 15		240x1	N	C	71	41	
12 18 17		1x60	CH	C	71	42	
12 19 37		480x1	N	C	71	41	
12 23 40		1x60	CH	C	71	42	
12 24 59		480x1	N	C	71	41	
12 29 03		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
12 30 19		480x1	N	C	71	41	
12 34 21		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
12 35 42		480x1	N	C	71	42	
12 39 45		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
12 40 57		480x1	N	C	71	41	
12 45 00		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
12 46 20		480x1	N	C	71	41	
12 50 22		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
12 51 37		240x1	Z	O	70	40	

Flight:

B299

KEY

Not Fitted

Fitted, Not Operated

Duff Data

Minor Problems

OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nezvorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Report Created 26/06/2007
15:49:19

Misc Core

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Fax machine:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H:

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Last Updated:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

ADA:

CCN:

CDP:

CIP 100:

CIP 25:

CPI:

CVI:

SID1:

SID2:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC 3025 (AMS):

INC:

VACC:

CPC 3010A (CVI):

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR:

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

26/06/2007 11:49:52

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B299

Date: 24 June 2007

Instruments

1. dry neph relative humidity suspect
2. nevz U/S
3. core chem. leak fixed

Aircraft

Satcom-H Calls

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

B299 Images Emailed In Flight

SDDI-20070624-0900-BNW-09-IR_108-05-600.jpg

EAA051 MSG dust product 24 Jun 2007 0900 UTC

0706240900_EAA051.jpg

EAA041 MSG dust RGB 24 Jun 2007 0900 UTC

0706240900_EEA041.jpg

EAA051 MSG dust product 24 Jun 2007 1100 UTC

0706241100_EAA051.jpg

EEA041 MSG dust RGB 24 Jun 2007 1100 UTC

0706241100_EEA041.jpg

EAA051 MSG dust product 24 Jun 2007 1300 UTC

0706241300_EAA051.jpg

EAA041 MSG dust RGB 24 Jun 2007 1300 UTC

0706241300_EEA041.jpg

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B299:

Log	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
Cloud Physics Processing	Processing yet to be completed.
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP log	No log as PSAP pump/filter info included on Flight Summary page
Wet Nephelometer	No operator on GERBIL

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	05 Sep 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Forward Facing Cameras
2 x Upward Facing Cameras
1 x Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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